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INFLUENCE OF H₂ CONTENT ON Fe, Al, AND Na RECOVERY DURING LOW-TEMPERATURE REDUCTION OF BAUXITE RESIDUE

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Introduction

Bauxite residue (BR) is produced in vast quantities during the Bayer process for producing alumina and is typically landfilled.^{1,2} Although numerous valorisation pathways have been suggested,^{3,4,5} the utilisation is currently restricted to <3% of the 170 Mt/year generated and a total volume of 4 Gt has been accumulated.^{2,6} The alkaline character, the fine particle size, as well as the complex nature of the minerals in BR, are the main technical reasons for the low utilisation.^{2,4} One of the valorisation options is the recovery of metals, such as iron, aluminium, titanium, and rare earth elements (REEs), including scandium. Our study investigated the reduction of BR with NaOH at relatively low temperatures (400-700°C) using varying contents of hydrogen as a reducing agent: 5 vol% H₂ + 95 vol% N₂ and 100 vol% H₂, both gas compositions with a flowrate of 20 L/h. A combined water leaching and wet-magnetic separation process was carried out for the recovery of Fe, Al, and Na. Unlike previous studies^{6,7,8}, this study provides a comprehensive comparison of Fe, Al, and Na recovery and further, evaluates phase changes under various H₂ concentrations, offering a novel contribution to the field.

Methodology

The BR utilised in this study was supplied by Mytilineos. After drying at 105°C, the BR was ground to a particle size of <500 µm. Analytical-grade NaOH was employed as an additive to BR. A 20 wt% NaOH pellets (with respect to 100 wt% of BR) were dissolved in 20 mL water and the resulting NaOH solution was mixed with BR to produce pellets by hand that ranged in size from 10-15 mm. The pellets were dried in an oven for 12 h at 105°C. The optimum process parameters, such as the temperature and NaOH dosage, were previously determined using thermodynamic modelling by FactSage analysis. Experimentally, approximately 100 g of pellets were used for each experiment and were reduced at 400, 500, 600, and 700°C for 2 h using the gas mix consisting of 5 vol% H₂ + 95 vol% N₂ with a flow rate of 20 L/h. For the experiments using pure hydrogen

atmosphere (100 vol% H₂), reduction took place at the same temperatures and flow rate, while the time was limited to 30 min. After reduction, 10 L/h of N₂ was injected to cool the pellets to room temperature. Subsequently, the reduced pellets were wet-milled with water in an RS200-type vibrating disk mill with a solid-to-liquid ratio of 0.5. After milling, the slurry was subjected to a combined water leaching and wet-magnetic separation process. For this purpose, the liquid-to-solid ratio of 10 was used. A standard magnetic block (0.2 Tesla) was placed inside a glass beaker and the slurry was stirred at 60°C for 60 min. This allowed the sodium aluminate solution, magnetic, and non-magnetic fractions to be separated concurrently. After separation, the magnetic block was removed to recover the magnetic fraction. The remaining non-magnetic solid fraction and leach liquor were separated using filter paper with a pore size of first 12 µm and 0.45 µm. The leach liquor was analysed using inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES). The solid products were characterised further using XRD.

The iron recovery rate was calculated using Equation (1). Furthermore, the recovery of aluminium and sodium was computed using Equation (2).

$$Fe \text{ Recovery} = \frac{(C*c)}{(F*f)} * 100 \quad (1)$$

$$Al \text{ (or) Na Recovery} = \frac{(cL*VL)}{((cL*VL)+(CSR*mSR))} * 100 \quad (2)$$

with C: weight of the concentrate (grade); c: assay of concentrate (%); F: weight of Feed (grade); t: assay of grade (%); cL: element concentration in the leachate solution (g/mL); VL: volume of analysed leachate solution (mL); CSR: elemental concentration in solid residue (mg/g); mSR: weight of solid residue (g)

Results and Discussion

When using a mix of hydrogen and nitrogen as gas mix (Figure 1), the intensity of Fe₂O₃ steadily decreased with increasing temperature, while that of Fe₃O₄ increased up to 600°C, indicating that ≥ 500°C was required for the complete conversion of hematite to the desired magnetite phase. At 700°C, however, Fe₃O₄ intensities were lower compared to 600°C and wüstite was detected. Thermodynamic calculations with FactSage indicate that when temperatures and hydrogen flow rates increase, wüstite (FeO) and sodium iron silicate (Na₂FeSiO₄) are formed

The maximum Fe recovery was measured to be 76.5%, as shown in Table 1, for 5 vol% H₂ + 95 vol% N₂ gas composition at 500°C, and ICP-OES data revealed that the maximum Al and Na recovery rates were 84.0% and 90.6%, respectively, at 700°C. The significant formation of wüstite, sodium aluminium silicate and sodium iron oxides observed from 600°C under pure H₂ (Figure 2) can have a deleterious impact on the recovery of Fe, Al,

and Na. This indicates that a higher concentration of H₂ can influence the formation of these phases. At 500°C, a maximum Fe recovery of 71.5% was reported. However, the highest recovery of Al and Na rose to 84.6% and 89.1%, respectively, at 700°C under 100 vol% H₂ reduction atmosphere (shown in Table 1).

Table 1: Recovery rates in dependence of temperature for the two gas mixes (flowrate 20 L/h)

Gas composition	Reduction temperature (°C)	Fe (%)	Al (%)	Na (%)
5 vol% H ₂ + 95 vol% N ₂	400	49.1	76.8	88.3
	500	76.5	80.2	89.7
	600	74.7	81.6	90.4
	700	53.3	84	90.6
100 vol% H ₂	400	39.5	54.5	74.2
	500	71.5	75.6	87.6
	600	67.6	80.4	88.3
	700	53.6	84.6	89.1

Figure 1: XRD patterns of Reduced BR samples from 400-700°C for 2 h with 20 wt% NaOH under 5 vol% H₂ + 95 vol% N₂

Figure 2: XRD patterns of Reduced BR samples from 400-700°C for 30 min with 20 wt% NaOH under 100 vol% H₂

Conclusions

The reduction studies of BR with 20 wt% NaOH under different hydrogen conditions (5 vol% H₂ + 95 vol% N₂, 100 vol% H₂) with 20 L/h flowrates were performed. Higher H₂ concentration promotes the formation of the undesired phases wüstite, sodium iron oxide, and sodium aluminium silicate, which negatively affect the recovery of Fe, Al, and Na during the downstream process. The phase formations are further confirmed in the thermodynamic calculations. However, similar recovery rates of Fe, Al, and Na were observed when the reduction was performed with 45 L/h flowrates 5 vol% H₂ + 95 vol% N₂. The findings presented in this study are promising as it seems that a low concentration of H₂ can effectively produce desirable phases such as magnetite and water-soluble sodium aluminate during the reduction of BR, resulting in comparable recovery rates for Fe, Al, and Na.

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